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BOUNDARY CONTROL IN A MODEL OF NONLINEAR VISCOUS FLUID MOTION

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Annotation: This paper investigates an optimal boundary control problem for the stationary flow of an incompressible nonlinear viscous fluid in a bounded domain of \mathbb{R}^n ($n = 2,3$). The control parameter is the surface force field acting on a part of the boundary. A weak formulation of the controlled system is introduced, and admissible solutions are defined. Under suitable assumptions on the viscosity function, the admissible control set, and the objective functional, the existence of an optimal solution minimising the cost functional is proved using the Galerkin method and monotonicity techniques.

Keywords: optimal boundary control, nonlinear viscous fluid, incompressible flow, weak solution, Galerkin method

ГРАНИЧНОЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ В МОДЕЛИ НЕЛИНЕЙНОГО ДВИЖЕНИЯ ВЯЗКОЙ ЖИДКОСТИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется задача оптимального граничного управления для стационарного течения несжимаемой нелинейной вязкой жидкости в ограниченной области R^n ($n=2,3$). Параметром управления является поле поверхностных сил, действующих на часть границы. Вводится слабая формулировка

управляемой системы и определяются допустимые решения. При соответствующих предположениях относительно функции вязкости, множества допустимых управляющих воздействий и целевого функционала существование оптимального решения, минимизирующего функционал стоимости, доказывается с использованием метода Галеркина и методов монотонности.

Ключевые слова: оптимальное граничное управление, нелинейная вязкая жидкость, несжимаемое течение, слабое решение, метод Галеркина

Introduction

Problems of control and optimisation in models of continuum mechanics have long attracted significant attention from specialists in control theory and its applications. In recent years, increasing interest has been devoted to boundary control problems for fluid flows (see, for example, [1-5] and the references therein). Such problems are of both theoretical and practical importance, since boundary control can be relatively easily implemented in real applications.

In this paper, we study an optimal boundary control problem for a system of equations describing the stationary motion of an incompressible nonlinear viscous fluid in a bounded domain of \mathbb{R}^n ($n = 2,3$) with a locally Lipschitz boundary. A distinctive feature of the considered problem is that the control parameter is the field of surface forces acting on a specified part of the boundary of the flow domain, rather than the boundary velocity field, which is usually assumed in boundary control models of fluid flow. This formulation makes it possible to study flow control in domains with impermeable solid boundaries without introducing external body forces as control parameters.

In this note, conditions are formulated under which generalised (weak) solutions of the controlled system exist that minimise a given objective functional.

It should be noted that numerous works have been devoted to the study of various mathematical problems related to models of nonlinear viscous fluid motion (see the monograph [6] and papers [7-10]). Despite this, the questions concerning the existence and properties of optimal solutions to the equations describing the motion of nonlinear viscous fluids

remain insufficiently studied. Some results are available only for the two-dimensional case. In particular, the stationary optimisation problem with control by external body forces was considered in the work of T. Slawig [11], while the corresponding nonstationary problem was studied by D. Wachsmuth and T. Rubicek [12-14].

Problem Statement and Main Result

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n (n = 2,3)$ be a bounded domain with a locally Lipschitz boundary Γ .

Consider the optimisation problem for the stationary flow of an incompressible nonlinear viscous fluid in the domain Ω :

$$v \cdot \nabla v - \text{Div}S + \nabla p = f \text{ in } \Omega, \tag{1}$$

$$S = \psi(I_2(v))D(v) \text{ in } \Omega, \tag{2}$$

$$\nabla \cdot v = 0 \text{ in } \Omega, \tag{3}$$

$$v \cdot n = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma, \tag{4}$$

$$v = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma \setminus \Gamma_c, \tag{5}$$

$$(S_n)_\tau = u \text{ on } \Gamma_c, \tag{6}$$

$$u \in U, \tag{7}$$

$$J(v, S, u) \rightarrow \inf. \tag{8}$$

Here v denotes the velocity field of the fluid, S is the deviator of the stress tensor, p is the pressure, and f is a given field of external forces. The tensor $D(v)$ is the strain-rate tensor defined by

$$D(v) = \frac{\nabla v + (\nabla v)^T}{2}.$$

Furthermore, $I_2(v)$ is the second invariant of the strain-rate tensor

$$I_2(v) = \sum_{i,j=1}^n D_{ij}^2(v).$$

The function $\psi: [0, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ is given, n is the unit outward normal vector to the boundary Γ , u is the control parameter, Γ_c is the part of the boundary where the control is applied, U is the set of admissible controls, and J is the prescribed objective functional.

We introduce the functional spaces used in the analysis of problems (1)-(8). Let $M_S^{n \times n}$ denote the space of symmetric $n \times n$ matrices with the Euclidean norm

$$\|A\|_{M_k^{n \times n}} = \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^n A_{ij}^2 \right)^{1/2},$$

for a matrix $A = (A_{ij}) \in M_S^{n \times n}$.

By $L^p(\Omega, F)$ and $W_q^m(\Omega, F)$ We denote the Lebesgue and Sobolev spaces, respectively, of functions $v: \Omega \rightarrow F$, where F is a finite-dimensional

space. The scalar product in $L^2(\Omega, F)$ is denoted by (\cdot, \cdot) . We also introduce the space

$$X(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n) = \{v \in W_2^1(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n): \nabla \cdot v = 0, v|_\Gamma \cdot n = 0, v|_{\Gamma \setminus \Gamma_c} = 0\} \quad (9)$$

with the norm $\|v\|_{X(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)} = \|D(v)\|_{L^2(\Omega, M_S^{n \times n})}$.

In formula (9), the trace of a function $v: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ from the space $W_2^1(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)$ on Γ is defined by $v|_\Gamma = \gamma_0 v$, where $\gamma_0: W_2^1(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow L^2(\Gamma, \mathbb{R}^n)$ is the trace operator.

In studying problem (1)-(8), we assume that the following conditions hold:

(i) the function ψ is continuous, and there exist positive constants α_1 and α_2 such that

$$\alpha_1 \leq \psi(s) \leq \alpha_2, s \in [0, +\infty);$$

(ii) for any $A, B \in M_S^{n \times n}$, the inequality

$$\left(\psi\left(\|A\|_{M_S^{n \times n}}^2\right)A - \psi\left(\|B\|_{M_S^{n \times n}}^2\right)B, A - B\right) \geq 0$$

holds;

(iii) the set U is bounded and sequentially weakly closed in the space

$$\{w \in L^2(\Gamma_c, \mathbb{R}^n): w \cdot n = 0\};$$

(iv) for any bounded set $Q \subset X(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n) \times L^2(\Omega, M_S^{n \times n}) \times L^2(\Gamma_c, \mathbb{R}^n)$,

$$\inf_{(v, S, u) \in Q} J(v, S, u) > -\infty;$$

(v) the functional

$$J: X(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n) \times L^2(\Omega, M_S^{n \times n}) \times L^2(\Gamma_c, \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

is weakly lower semicontinuous.

Let $f \in L^2(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)$.

Definition 1.

A triple $(v, S, u) \in X(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n) \times L^2(\Omega, M_S^{n \times n}) \times L^2(\Gamma_c, \mathbb{R}^n)$ is called an admissible triple of the controlled system (1)-(7) if relation (2) holds, inclusion (7) is satisfied, and the identity

$$-\sum_{i=1}^n \left(v_i v, \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x_i}\right) + (\psi(I_2(v))D(v), D(\varphi)) = (f, \varphi) + \int_{\Gamma_c} u \cdot \varphi d\Gamma_c \quad (10)$$

holds for every $\varphi \in X(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)$.

Remark.

The appearance of identity (10) in the definition of an admissible triple corresponds to the well-known approach used in the study of generalised (weak) solutions of hydrodynamic models with slip conditions on the boundary.

Let M denote the set of admissible triples of problem (1)-(7).

Definition 2.

A triple $(v^*, S^*, u^*) \in M$ is called a solution of the optimisation problem (1)-(8) if

$$J(v^*, S^*, u^*) = \inf_{(v, S, u) \in M} J(v, S, u).$$

We now formulate the main result of the paper.

Theorem.

Suppose that conditions (i)–(v) are satisfied. Then the optimisation problem (1)-(8) admits at least one solution.

To prove this theorem, methods of topological degree theory, the Galerkin method, and the monotonicity property of the constitutive relation (2) are used.

Conclusions

In this paper, an optimal boundary control problem for the stationary motion of an incompressible nonlinear viscous fluid in a bounded domain has been studied. The control parameter was taken as the field of surface forces acting on a specified part of the boundary, which makes it possible to consider flow control in domains with impermeable rigid boundaries. A weak formulation of the controlled system was introduced, and the concept of admissible triples was defined.

Under appropriate assumptions on the viscosity function, the admissible control set, and the objective functional, the existence of an optimal solution minimising the given cost functional was proved. The proof was based on the Galerkin method, properties of monotone operators, and compactness arguments.

The obtained results contribute to the theoretical study of optimal boundary control problems for nonlinear hydrodynamic models and can serve as a basis for further investigations of more general models and numerical approaches.

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